

Inca

By Charles Stanish, UCLA

Entry tags: Religious Group, South American Religions, Inca Religion

Inca empire in pre-Columbian South America

Date Range: 1300 CE - 1550 CE

Region: Peru

Region tags: South America, Peru

Peru

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Cobo, Bernabe. Inca Religion and Customs.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

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– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

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Architecture, Geography

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↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: display of mummies

– Yes [specify]: Display of mummies

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

– No

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

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Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

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– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No